

Subject: Fw: Williamson Collection

Date: Tue, 13 Aug 2002 09:59:42 +0100

From: "Derek Kennet" <derek.kennet@durham.ac.uk>

To: "Priestman, Seth" <seth.priestman@durham.ac.uk>

Dear Seth

Useful reply from Sumner below.

BIPS have sent the proofs of our Iran article. Pop by when you want to have a look. We need to send them back soon.

Derek

----- Original Message -----

From: William M. Sumner <sumner.1@osu.edu>

To: Derek Kennet <derek.kennet@durham.ac.uk>

Sent: Monday, August 12, 2002 7:25 PM

Subject: Re: Williamson Collection

> Dear Prof. Kennet, It's certainly good news to hear that someone is
> working on Andrew's Iranian ceramic collection. You wrote in part:
>
> >I have been
> >advised by them to contact you regarding three questions:
> >
> >1. We are unsure of Williamson's policy on pre-Sasanian pottery. There is
> >very little of it in the collection. It is possible that: a) there was
none
> >in the area he worked in (unlikely), b) he did not collect it, c) he
> >collected it and it has been separated and is stored somewhere else (with
M
> >Prickett's material?, at Tepe Yayha?, at the archaeology museum in
Tehran?).
> >Do you have any knowledge about Williamson's pre-historic collection
> >strategy and, if he collected pre-historic pottery, where it might now
be?
>
> Andrew was not particularly interested in pre-Sasanian pottery.
> When he and I traveled together up into the high valley around Asupas
> and Se Deh in a failed effort to get to Dez-i Khord he only collected
> at Islamic sites. At my request he and Martha Prickett made
> collections at about a dozen prehistoric sites in the valley behind
> Persepolis (Khafrak Sofla) and in the area to be flooded by the Dorud
> Zan dam, then under construction. All of the Achaemenid and earlier
> pottery he collected on these two sorties became a part of my
> collection and is now at Univ. Of Pennsylvania. All of the
> Sasanian-Islamic pottery I collected in the Marv Dasht was turned
> over to Andrew for publication. He sorted it in Iran--some he stored
> at the Asia Institute in Shiraz, some he stored at the British
> Institute in Tehran (transferred to Iran Bastan when BIPS moved
> north), and a selection, including the painted Islamic ware that I
> dubbed "Madabad Ware," he shipped to Oxford. I have correspondence
> from Martha Prickett on the location of the collections that I will
> send to you by mail.
> Andrew's main survey work was done in other districts, not the
> Marv Dasht. Martha was his faithful companion and survey slavey
> during quite a bit of his work along the Gulf coast. Sadly, she died
> of cancer last year. My guess is that any prehistoric pottery
> collected when they were together would have been Martha's to publish
> and would have been stored with her dissertation collection from
> around Yahya. I rather doubt that Andrew collected prehistoric
> sherds when he was working alone, but perhaps I do him an injustice.
> >
> >2. We have some limited material from your sites from the Merv Dasht

survey

> >(all hand-made painted ware). We have been able to locate the sites from
Don

> >Whitcomb's article, but wonder if there may be a fuller and more precise
> >list of site locations from that survey that we do not know about.

>

> There is an unpublished site inventory for the Marv Masht with maps.
> I'll send a copy. Don Whitcomb and I published a paper in the
> Stronach festschrift with illustrations of a few Madabad sherds; Don
> has Madabad sherds on loan from the Ashmolean unless he has returned
> them recently.

>

> >3. Locating Williamson's sites is very difficult as there are no maps or
> >notebooks that give the site locations. All we have is a series of cards
> >with site numbers and occasional toponyms. Did Williamson keep maps? We
> >assume he must have done. Do you have any copies of or know where they

may

> >be?

>

> Unhappily, I do not know of any maps or notes for Andrew's surveys.
> In those days good maps were nigh impossible to get; we used the
> awful ozilid "Gendarm" maps (1:50,000) and the USAF aerial approach
> charts (1:250,000), and sometimes the old British quarter inch
> series. Andrew probably used some of these and he may also have used
> some of Sir Aurel Stein's maps. soon after Andrew died Martha
> initiated a plan to publish Andrew's surveys and she may have gotten
> hold of the maps and notes, if any. She later abandoned the project.

>

> >Lastly we would be very interested in any information or notes that may
shed

> >some light on the way Williamson worked.

>

> It was pretty much drive until you see a site, walk the surface,
> do a bit of compass and pacing for a sketch map, if any. The great
> day of large survey crews conducting systematic sampling using GPS
> was a dream we didn't even have. Andrew had a good grasp of early
> Islamic geography and used it well. Not much help, but I'll try to
> get the mail items off this week. Best wishes for the project.

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> You are invited to visit the Malyan, Iran, archaeological web site
> at: <http://home.columbus.rr.com/malyan/>